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Research Article

Comparing Efficiency Of Antimicrobial Photodynamic Therapy (aPDT),
Scaling And Root Planing (SRP) And Combination Therapy (aPDT+SRP)
In Patients With Chronic Periodontitis

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ABSTRACT

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Background: Nonsurgical periodontal therapy is considered to be the gold standard treatment for periodontal diseases. Scaling and root planing, although eliminates the local factors, however are ineffective in completely eliminating the subgingival periodontal pathogens. Hence, instead of using antibiotics for such use, an effective means of eradicating such bacteria would be using antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT).

Materials & Methods: 40 patients diagnosed with chronic periodontitis in the age group of 30-60 years were randomly selected for the study. A split mouth design was employed in which patients mouth were divided in to 3 treatment groups: Scaling and Root planing (SRP) as control group and antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT) and combination therapy (SRP+aPDT) as the test groups. Antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT) consisted of using a diode laser at 1 W, 600-700 WL, with a photosensitizer methylene blue placed in periodontal pockets for 60 sec. All the clinical parameters like plaque index (PI), gingival index (GI), probing pocket depth, relative attachment level were evaluated at baseline 1 month, 3 months and 6 months' time duration.

Results: The study showed reduction in all clinical parameters in combination therapy. aPDT provided best results when combined with mechanical instrumentation as compared to only monotherapy.

Conclusions: Within the limitation of the study it can be concluded that photodynamic therapy as an adjunct to classical scaling and root planing can be recommended as effective treatment option in chronic periodontitis case

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INTRODUCTION:

Periodontitis, an inflammatory disease caused by anaerobic bacteria, is one of the cause for tooth loss in adults.^{1,2} The plaque biofilm contains numerous bacteria which co-aggregate, resulting in development of a well-established ecological niche. Further, they colonize to periodontal pockets and invade the tissue at varying depths. Hence, elimination of this bacteria is essential for successful therapy.² The non-surgical therapy has greatest advantage of providing a tissue friendly approach at low cost and with least complications.² Scaling and root planing² (SRP), Local Drug Delivery (LDD)³, systemic antimicrobial therapy, antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT) are few of the nonsurgical treatment modalities.⁴ SRP is considered to be the standard therapy for any plaque induced periodontal disease, as it eliminates the biofilm. However, some studies have shown inability of SRP in completely eliminating all subgingival pathogens.⁵ Hence adjuvant therapy using LDD or systemic antimicrobial therapy has been advocated with superior results.³

Usage of antimicrobials either locally or systemically is not without concerns. Exposing non-diseased parts of the body for side effects like GIT, superinfections, antibiotic resistance are few non-desirable outcomes of systemic antimicrobial photodynamic therapy.⁵ Although LDD has overcome the above side effects by targeting the pathogens using higher concentration of drug at diseased sites, still injudicious repeated applications may change the ecoflora resulting in overgrowth of resistant microbes.³ Antimicrobial photodynamic therapy is an alternative therapy indicated for treatment of microbial infections, cancer, ophthalmological and dermatological disorders & in treating periodontal disease.⁶

This process requires placement of a photosensitizer inside the pdl pocket, and

activating it by means of a low level laser energy with a specific wavelength to excite it from a singlet to double or triplet state. This leads to formation of singlet oxygen species which damage the bacterial cells. This lethal photosensitization has been found to be effective against multidrug resistant microbe's as well as usual pathogenic flora of the pockets. Further, the effect of aPDT is much more rapid when compared to LDD and no evidence of aPDT resistance has been reported.⁴ Hence the present study was undertaken to evaluate the effectiveness of aPDT as a monotherapy and as an adjunct to SRP in treatment of chronic periodontitis.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

40 Chronic Periodontitis Patients were randomly selected with in the age group of 35-60 years, having probing pocket depth between 4 to 6 mm with atleast 20 teeth and no history of allergic to methylene blue or usage of antibiotics / NSAID's since past 6 months. Teeth having extensive caries or gingival morphological alterations or where CEJ was difficult to determine were excluded as they could impair the outcome of the study.

Study subjects were treated with 3 different treatment modalities using a split mouth design as site A (SRP), site B (aPDT), site C (SRP+aPDT). Clinical parameters such as PI (plaque index) by Sillness and Loe, GI (gingival index) by Loe and Sillness, PPD (probing pocket depth), GBI (gingival bleeding index) by Ainamo and Bay, RAL (relative attachment level) were recorded at baseline, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months' time duration. A Photosensitizer consisting of freshly prepared 3, 7 bis (dimethyl-amino) phenazathionium chloride trihydrate [Methylene blue (MB) M9140 Sigma-Aldrich] (figure 1) suspended in double distilled water at a concentration of 10mg/ml was used as the dye. (figure 2)

Figure 1: Photosensitizer dye Methylene blue (MB) M9140 Sigma-Aldrich]

Figure 2: Methylene blue suspended in double distilled water at a concentration of 10mg/ml

Figure 3: Antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (Step 1)
[Two milliliter of Methylene Blue applied topically to site with 6mm pocket depth for 60 seconds using a syringe]

The Photodynamic Therapy was performed using a diode laser operating at 600-900nm with CW output power of 1W.⁷ Two milliliter of Methylene Blue (MB) was applied topically to site with 4-6mm pocket depth for 60 seconds using a syringe (figure 3), after 3 minutes the site was irrigated with distilled

water to flush out excess MB (figure 4).^{7,8} The laser beam was guided through a flexible fiberoptic cable kept in non-contact mode for one minute (figure 5). Patients were given oral hygiene instructions and recalled at 1 week, 1 month, 3 months, and 6 months to evaluate for all clinical parameters.

Figure 4: Antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (Step 2)
[After 3 minutes the site was irrigated with distilled water to flushout excess MB]

Figure 5: Antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (Step 3)
[The laser beam was guided through a flexible fiber-optic cable for one minute]

**Baseline: probing pocket depth
6mm**

**6 months: probing pocket depth
3mm**

**Figure 6: Scaling and Root Planing group
[SRP (Group 1)] follow up**

Statistical analysis:

Data were tabulated and statistically analysed using SPSS statistical software version 21 by IBM Corporation. Kruskal Wallis and ANOVA tests were used for intragroup and Mann-Whitney U test was used for intergroup comparison of plaque index score and gingival index score. One way ANOVA was used to evaluate intragroup and Tukeys multiple posthoc procedue used for intergroup

comparison for probing pocket depth, relative attachment level and gingival bleeding score. Wilcoxon matched pairs test were used to evaluate change in percentage at 1 month, 3 months and 6 months' time duration for plaque index score and gingival index score. Paired test were used to evaluate change in percentage at 1 month, 3 months and 6 months for probing pocket depth, relative attachment level and gingival bleeding score.

Baseline: probing pocket depth
6mm

6 months: probing pocket depth
3mm

Figure 7: Antimicrobial photodynamic therapy group [aPDT (Group 2)] follow up

Baseline: probing pocket depth
6mm

6 months: probing pocket depth
4mm

Figure 8: Combination therapy group [SRP+aPDT (Group 3)] follow up

RESULTS

There was a reduction in plaque index score and gingival index score in all the groups at all review intervals when compared to baseline. (Table 1, table 2, graph 1, graph 2). Similarly reduction was observed in gingival bleeding associated with pocket depth reduction in the groups at varying intervals of time (table 3, table 4, graph 3, graph 4).

Table 1 : Comparison of three groups (1, 2, 3) with respect to plaque index scores at baseline, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months time points by Kruskal Wallis ANOVA

Groups	Baseline		1 month		3 months		6 months		Changes from baseline to					
									1 month		3 months		6 months	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Group 1	1.16	0.43	0.25	0.23	0.27	0.13	0.51	0.16	0.90	0.48	0.89	0.44	0.65	0.48
Group 2	1.16	0.45	0.88	0.50	0.91	0.49	0.94	0.30	0.27	0.53	0.25	0.65	0.22	0.52
Group 3	1.15	0.49	0.10	0.07	0.11	0.09	0.60	2.18	1.05	0.50	1.04	0.52	0.55	2.22
% of change in Group 1									78.08%#, p=0.0001*		76.95%#, p=0.0001*		56.30%#, p=0.0001*	
% of change in Group 2									23.75%#, p=0.0001*		21.33%#, p=0.0001*		18.67%#, p=0.0001*	
% of change in Group 3									91.56%#, p=0.0001*		90.21%#, p=0.0001*		47.60%#, p=0.0001*	
H-value	0.1150		78.3600		80.1700		80.9490		37.3570		34.3370		23.5900	
P-value	0.9940		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*	
Pair wise comparisons of groups by Mann-Whitney U test														
Group 1 vs Group 2	p=0.7472		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0002*	
Group 1 vs Group 3	p=0.9731		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.1795		p=0.1842		p=0.1009	
Group 2 vs Group 3	p=0.7545		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*	

*p<0.05, # applied Wilcoxon matched pairs test
 Group 1(Control group) : Scaling and root planing (SRP)
 Group 2(Test group): antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT)
 Group 3(Test group): Combination therapy (SRP+aPDT)

Chart no 1: Comparison of three group (1,2,3) with respect to plaque index scores at baseline, 1month, 3 months and 6 months' time points

Group 1(Control group): Scaling and root planing (SRP)
 Group 2(Test group): antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT)
 Group 3(Test group): Combination therapy (SRP+aPDT)

Table 2: Comparison of three groups (1, 2, 3) with respect to gingival index scores at baseline, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months time points by Kruskal Wallis ANOVA

Groups	Baseline		1 month		3 months		6 months		Changes from baseline to					
									1 month		3 months		6 months	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Group 1	2.00	0.28	0.58	0.30	0.33	0.18	0.51	0.20	1.41	0.32	1.67	0.31	1.49	0.37
Group 2	1.95	0.25	1.05	0.32	0.91	0.26	0.96	0.22	0.89	0.28	1.04	0.30	0.99	0.28
Group 3	2.05	0.21	0.40	0.40	0.11	0.17	0.63	2.18	1.65	0.43	1.94	0.23	1.42	2.15
% of change in Group 1									70.76%#, p=0.0001*		83.47%#, p=0.0001*		74.54%#, p=0.0001*	
% of change in Group 2									45.84%#, p=0.0001*		53.30%#, p=0.0001*		50.73%#, p=0.0001*	
% of change in Group 3									80.65%#, p=0.0001*		94.80%#, p=0.0001*		69.31%#, p=0.0001*	
H-value	2.8981		53.3690		87.7180		70.4290		58.3650		78.6380		58.0450	
P-value	0.2348		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*	
Pair wise comparisons of groups by Mann-Whitney U test														
Group 1 vs Group 2	p=0.3100		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*	
Group 1 vs Group 3	p=0.7003		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0004*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0026*	
Group 2 vs Group 3	p=0.1629		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*	

*p<0.05, # applied Wilcoxon matched pairs test

Group 1(Control group): Scaling and root planing (SRP)

Group 2(Test group): antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT)

Group 3(Test group): Combination therapy (SRP+aPDT)

Chart no 2: Comparison of three groups (1,2,3) with respect to gingival index scores at baseline, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months' time point.

Group 1(Control group): Scaling and root planing (SRP)

Group 2(Test group): antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT)

Group 3(Test group): Combination therapy (SRP+aPDT)

Table 3: Comparison of three groups (1, 2, 3) with respect to Probing pocket depth (PPD) scores at baseline, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months time points by One way ANOVA

Groups	Baseline		1 month		3 months		6 months		Changes from baseline to					
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	1 month		3 months		6 months	
Group 1	5.89	0.16	4.60	0.39	4.21	0.31	4.20	0.33	1.29	0.31	1.68	0.31	1.69	0.30
Group 2	5.86	0.21	4.84	0.48	4.61	0.42	4.49	0.44	1.01	0.47	1.25	0.45	1.36	0.45
Group 3	5.67	1.12	4.05	0.83	2.78	0.61	2.69	0.66	1.63	1.09	2.90	1.02	2.98	1.07
% of change in Group 1									21.83%#, p=0.0001*		28.58%#, p=0.0001*		28.76%#, p=0.0001*	
% of change in Group 2									17.29%#, p=0.0001*		21.32%#, p=0.0001*		23.24%#, p=0.0001*	
% of change in Group 3									28.67%#, p=0.0001*		51.06%#, p=0.0001*		52.51%#, p=0.0001*	
F-value	1.2130		18.8009		171.1398		152.1651		7.5168		64.9002		61.0553	
P-value	0.3010		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*	
Pair wise comparisons of groups by Tukeys multiple posthoc procedure														
Group 1 vs Group 2	p=0.9741		p=0.1816		p=0.0008*		p=0.0234*		p=0.2097		p=0.0139*		p=0.0902	
Group 1 vs Group 3	p=0.3248		p=0.0003*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0877		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*	
Group 2 vs Group 3	p=0.4401		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0006*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*	

*p<0.05, # applied paired t test

Group 1(Control group): Scaling and root planing (SRP)

Group 2(Test group): antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT)

Group 3(Test group): Combination therapy (SRP+aPDT)

Chart no 3: Comparison of three groups(1,2,3) with respect to probing pocket depth(PPD) scores at baseline, 1month, 3months and 6 months' time point.

Group 1(Control group): Scaling and root planing (SRP)
 Group 2(Test group): antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT)
 Group 3(Test group): Combination therapy (SRP+aPDT)

Table 4: Comparison of three groups (1, 2, 3) with respect to GBI(%) scores at baseline, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months time points by One way ANOVA

Groups	Baseline		1 month		3 months		6 months		Changes from baseline to					
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	1 month		3 months		6 months	
Group 1	100.0	0.00	28.62	10.54	11.43	9.26	19.64	15.06	71.38	10.54	88.57	9.26	80.36	15.06
Group 2	100.0	0.00	41.78	11.38	28.93	15.68	36.72	16.57	58.22	11.38	71.07	15.68	63.28	16.57
Group 3	100.0	0.00	21.74	10.75	6.43	7.19	15.03	23.52	78.26	10.75	93.57	7.19	84.97	23.52
% of change in Group 1									71.38%#, p=0.0001*		88.57%#, p=0.0001*		80.36%#, p=0.0001*	
% of change in Group 2									58.22%#, p=0.0001*		71.07%#, p=0.0001*		63.28%#, p=0.0001*	
% of change in Group 3									78.26%#, p=0.0001*		93.57%#, p=0.0001*		84.97%#, p=0.0001*	
F-value	0.0000		34.9254		43.6990		14.8607		34.9254		43.6990		14.8607	
P-value	1.0000		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*	
Pair wise comparisons of groups by Tukeys multiple posthoc procedure														
Group 1 vs Group 2	P=1.0000		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0003*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0003*	
Group 1 vs Group 3	P=1.0000		p=0.0155*		p=0.1222		p=0.5167		p=0.0155*		p=0.1222		p=0.5167	
Group 2 vs Group 3	P=1.0000		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*	

*p<0.05, # applied paired t test

Group 1(Control group): Scaling and root planing (SRP)
 Group 2(Test group): antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT)
 Group 3(Test group): Combination therapy (SRP+aPDT)

Chart no 4: Comparison of three groups (1,2,3) with respect to Gingival bleeding index (GBI) score at baseline, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months' time point.

Group 1(Control group): Scaling and root planing (SRP)
 Group 2(Test group): antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT)
 Group 3(Test group): Combination therapy (SRP+aPDT)

However, greatest reduction in all the parameters were exhibited in combination therapy group, which exhibited lesser plaque and gingival index score and a significant gain in attachment level (table 5 , graph 5). Although the SRP

group and aPDT group demonstrated reduction of all parameters and gain in attachment level, it was found that SRP group fared better in gain in attachment level (12.8%) than aPDT (9.8%) as monotherapy (table 5, graph 5).

Table 5: Comparison of three groups (1, 2, 3) with respect to Relative attachment level(RAL) scores at baseline, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months time points by One way ANOVA

Groups	Baseline		1 month		3 months		6 months		Changes from baseline to					
									1 month		3 months		6 months	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Group 1	14.04	0.97	12.69	1.06	11.96	2.02	12.24	1.15	1.35	0.36	2.08	1.87	1.80	0.46
Group 2	13.95	0.98	12.98	1.08	12.88	1.36	12.57	1.15	0.97	0.28	1.07	1.06	1.38	0.52
Group 3	14.09	0.77	12.27	0.87	10.99	0.90	10.88	0.84	1.83	0.39	3.10	0.63	3.21	0.50
% of change in Group 1									9.60%#, p=0.0001*		14.79%#, p=0.0001*		12.84%#, p=0.0001*	
% of change in Group 2									6.95%#, p=0.0001*		7.66%#, p=0.0001*		9.88%#, p=0.0001*	
% of change in Group 3									12.96%#, p=0.0001*		21.99%#, p=0.0001*		22.79	
F-value	0.2546		5.0691		15.7756		28.5857		61.7687		24.7071		151.7437	
P-value	0.7757		0.0077*		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*		0.0001*	
Pair wise comparisons of groups by Tukeys multiple posthoc procedure														
Group 1 vs Group 2	p=0.9004		p=0.4084		p=0.0196*		p=0.3356		p=0.0001*		p=0.0021*		p=0.0007*	
Group 1 vs Group 3	p=0.9605		p=0.1481		p=0.0131*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0018*		p=0.0001*	
Group 2 vs Group 3	p=0.7599		p=0.0057*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*		p=0.0001*	

*p<0.05, # applied paired t test

Group 1(Control group): Scaling and root planing (SRP)

Group 2(Test group): antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT)

Group 3(Test group): Combination therapy (SRP+aPDT)

Chart no 5: Comparison of three groups (1,2,3) with respect to Relative attachment level (RAL) score at baseline, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months' time point.

Group 1(Control group): Scaling and root planing (SRP)

Group 2(Test group): antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT)

Group 3(Test group): Combination therapy (SRP+aPDT)

DISCUSSION

In the present study a split mouth design was employed wherein three groups, SRP, PDT as a monotherapy and combination therapy (SRP+PDT) were evaluated. Methylene blue, the photosensitizer used in the present study lacked any antimicrobial action all by itself, hence did not influence the study design or the results of the study. All the treatment modalities showed clinical benefits and were statistically significant.

There was a statistically significant reduction in the probing pocket depth (PPD) in the combination therapy group (SRP+aPDT) on comparison with the monotherapy using SRP and aPDT which suggest additional clinical benefit of PDT along with SRP in reducing periodontal pockets depth. A reduction in PPD signifies resolution of inflammation thereby arresting progressive periodontal breakdown. These results are comparable to that of Braun et al⁹, Pineheiro et al¹⁰, Ge et al¹¹, Berkdar et al¹² and Alweli et al¹³ where similar probing depth reduction were reported. Although some studies did differ for the same parameters^{15,15,16} an overwhelming number of studies have shown combination therapy to be far superior to monotherapy.^{12,17,18,19,20,21}

In the present study aPDT as a monotherapy showed very little improvement in PPD reduction, aPDT alone did not provide superior effectiveness in terms of clinical attachment level gain when compared to SRP and combination therapy.²¹ This could be due to the fact that PDT can be effective only when a plaque thickness is less than 10 µm, above which it has no effect²². Amir et al²³ in their systematic review pointed that PDT as independent treatment was not superior to SRP. On the contrary, Rafael et al²⁴ in aggressive periodontitis patients showed PDT to provide similar benefits as SRP, which could be attributed to PDT targeting Aa and Pg extensively.^{24,25,26}

Romos et al²⁷ reported SRP+PDT to be better in reducing probing pocket depth than SRP + Antibiotics in type 2 diabetic patients. Studies in systemically healthy patients have found combination therapy to be superior to SRP alone.^{12,17,19} Studies in aggressive periodontitis patients¹⁸ and HIV patients²⁸ have also shown combination therapy to fair better

than monotherapy. The present study supports that this combination therapy to be superior to monotherapy in reducing PPD reduction and Attachment level gain.

Although reduction in gingival index (GI) in all the three groups were observed, SRP alone can reduce clinical inflammation and hence there is insufficient evidence to support the use of aPDT alone as alternative treatment to SRP. Studies have shown similar improvement in all clinical parameters in SRP and combination therapy groups.²⁹

There was a reduction in plaque index in SRP and combination therapy groups for a short period of 3 months. Systematic review and meta-analysis done by Fabrizio S et al suggest that adjunctive PDT provides short-term benefits in term of CAL gain, PPD reduction, PI, GI, GBI score at 3 months. No significant effects were observed after 6 months. Studies have shown plaque index to decrease even in placebo groups just by reinforcement of oral hygiene alone.³⁰

Bleeding on probing (BOP) data was reported in different ways by various authors, because of the heterogeneity in methods of assessment. In present study statistically significant reduction was seen in GBI in combination group followed by SRP and aPDT at 1 month and 3 month, however slight increase in the GBI score was noticed at 6 months. This reduction in gingival bleeding can be attributed to the marked reduction in both bacterial load and inflammation observed initially after the therapy. Andersen et al²¹ reported that BOP improved from base-line in all groups at 12 weeks. Oliveira R et al³⁰ reported a marked improvement in bleeding scores in PDT and SRP groups. Braun A et al⁹ reported improvement in both PDT and SRP, with lower values in the PDT group. However Yilmaz S et al³¹ failed to demonstrate a significant difference in BOP between SRP and SRP+PDT group, though these values were significantly lower than baseline values.

Chandres et al reported that in patients under supportive periodontal therapy the additional application of single episode of aPDT to SRP failed to result in an additional improvement in terms of pocket depth reduction and gain of attachment, but it resulted in significantly higher reduction in bleeding score than following SRP alone.¹⁵ Veronique et al²⁰ reported 2 PDT application weekly resulted in better result.

PDT aims in affecting a susceptible host, presence of pathogenic flora and absence of beneficial species; by removing the pathogenic species and neutralizing cytokines responsible for further destruction, indirectly promoting the growth of healthy flora there by modifying the destructive cascade.

CONCLUSION

The results of present study showed improvement in clinical parameters in all three groups, but higher reduction was observed in combination therapy followed by SRP and aPDT. All groups yielded reduction in clinical parameters. No subjects reported with side effects or worsening of disease. All clinical parameters seemed to stabilize by the end of 3 months. Combination therapy was foremost in reducing PI, GI, GBI, PPD and attachment loss when compared to remaining two groups- SRP and PDT. PDT alone was behind SRP and Combination therapy group in reducing the clinical parameters. There was a minimal increase in plaque index score, gingival index score and gingival bleeding index score when observed at 6 months compared to 3 months which shows that repeated PDT adjunct with SRP was required for long time management of chronic periodontitis case.

Thus the present study indicates that the adjunctive use of aPDT has a positive effect on treatment outcomes. By adding antimicrobial photodynamic treatment procedure to conventional anti-infective approaches, it might be possible to improve non-surgical periodontal therapy. Further studies have to be directed to know the long term impact of adjunctive PDT in patients with chronic or aggressive periodontitis or the use of this procedure as a routine treatment during maintenance therapy. Hence within the limitation of this present study it can be concluded that the photodynamic therapy as adjunct to classical scaling and root planing can be recommended as treatment option in chronic periodontitis case however, it can by no means replace the classical therapy concept since an observation period of six months was comparatively short.

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